

NĀGARĪ ALPHABET, SIGNS AND SYMBOLS OF PARAMĀRA INSCRIPTIONS

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The Paramāras, started their political career in the ninth century C.E. as feudatories of the imperial Rāc̄mrakūṃṃ monarch¹, succeeded in building a strong kingdom in the heart of the central India in the tenth century and played a leading role in the history of the country till fourteenth century C.E. During the course of their political existence, the Paramāras ruled over various territories, which includes Mālava proper as well the adjacent districts of Vidishā in the east, Ratlām in the west, Indore and the parts of Hoshangābād in the south-east. In addition the imperial royal house of Mālava, there was other contemporary royal houses of the Paramāras over Arbuda-manda, Maru-mandala, Jālor, and Vāga. The house that grew to power in the region around Arbuda-maandala or Mount Ābū, subsequently extended their territories in the neighboring region of Bhinmāl-Kirādū, and Jālor and those houses were known after these places. The rulers of all these houses were semi-independent chiefs. Paramāras of the Ābū branch owed their fidelity to the Caulukya dynasty, while those at Vāgada were subordinate to the main line of Mālava.

Poets, Scribes and Engravers of the Paramāra Inscriptions:

In general, inscriptions of the Paramāras are composed by distinguished poets⁵, written (possibly copied) by skilled scribes, and incised by engravers. The engraver incised the letters according to the drawing to retain the accuracy and perform his work neatly. However, this practice is not universal, as in some instances, the job of all three categories, namely the author,

the scribe and the engraver was performed by the same person. The relevant epigraphic data provide significant details concerning these professionals, and sometimes mention their predecessors as well as native place, role, occupation and designation as applied to poets, scribes and engravers. It is obvious from the examples of good epigraphic poetry that high talented poets were employed for composing the inscriptions. The poets were honored by different ways, even by donating land. Atrū stone inscription of the time of JayasiAha: V.S. 1314 (C.E. 1258) records the donation by JayasiAhadeva of the village Mhaisadā (Bhairnā) in the territorial division of PaAvīmha in favor of a *kavicakravartin*, *mhakkura NārāyaGa* (no. 55). Tilakwādā copper-plate inscription of the time of Bhojadeva: V.S. 1103 (C.E. 1046) was composed by Sobhika, son of the Kāyastha Aiyala of the Vālabhya family, at the request of the king (no. 15) and with an appeal to excuse him for the mistakes that may have occurred in the composition, "ūnātiriktamajñānāllikhitam sūāsaneṭra yat/pramnameva kartavyam samta% sarvvasahāyatah". Pandita Mahipala, son of Pandita Srngavasa was the poet of Udaipur stone inscription of the time of Udayāditya: V.S. 1137 (C.E.1080) (no.19). The poet Aúvatthāma composed the verses of the Jainād stone inscription of the time of Jagaddeva (no. 29). The composition is here said to be heart-touching, "hridayamgama", and this epithet is really befitting in view of its pleasing, elegant and graceful style. Nāgpur Museum stone inscription of Naravarman: V.S. 1161 (C.E. 1105) stated to have been adorned with many eulogies and hymns composed by the

king himself "*tena svayamkrtāneka-praūastistaticitritam*" (no. 33). The record of the Vidishā stone inscription of the time of Naravarman was composed by *mhakkura* Úrī Mādhava, a son of the *mhakkura* Sūpama and a grandson of *mhakkura* Nījāsa and a *dvija* belonging to the Māthura clan (no. 36). Eulogy of the Sun-God was composed by Pandita Chittapa, who enjoyed the title of *maḥākavi-cakravartin*. Sircar agrees with Thomas who held that Chittapa was a contemporary and probably a court-poet of the Paramāra king Bhoja (no. 37). Madana was a renowned poet who composes at least four inscriptions of the Paramāras. Piplānagar copper-plate inscription of Arjunavarman: V.S. 1267 (C.E. 1211) was composed by Rājaguru Madana at the instance of *mahā-pandita* Úrī BilhaGa (no. 47). Two Sehore copper-plate inscriptions of Arjunavarman: V.S. 1270 (C.E. 1213) and 1272 (C.E. 1215) were also composed by the same poet but first was composed with the consent of BilhaGa as *mahāsāndhivigrahika* while the second with the consent of Rājā SalakhaGa as the *mahāsāndhivigrahika* (nos. 48, 49). Māndhātā copper-plate inscription of Devapāla: V.S. 1282 (C.E. 1225) was also composed by Madana (no. 51). Harsaudā stone inscription of the time of Devapāla: V.S. 1275 (C.E. 1218) was composed by Devaúarmana (no. 50). The learned BrāhmaGa Vāmana was the poet of the eulogy of the Modī stone inscription of the time of Jayavarmadeva: V.S. 1314 (C.E. 1258) who composed it in „*sadalamkāra* (no. 56). Māndhātā copper-plate inscription of Jayavarman: V.S. 1317 (C.E. 1261) was written (*likhitam rājauāsanam*), probably composed by the learned Harcadeva, the son of the learned Gavīúa, under the approbation of Pandita Mālādhara, who was employed a minister of war and treaty by the *mahārājādhirāja* Úrī Jayavarmadeva at Mandapa-durga, and that it was revised by the grammarian (*úābdika*) Āmadeva, a disciple of the wise Goseka who was well versed

in legal science, "*smṛti-úāstra*" (no. 57). Other Māndhātā copper-plate inscription of Jayavarman: V.S. 1331 (C.E. 1274) was composed by ÚrīkaGmha, who was a member of the assembly of Jayavarman and Trivedin by heritage, "*kulakramāyāt[traividyatvena]*" and appointed by the king himself (no. 60). Vasantagadh stone inscription of the time of Pūrnapāla: V.S. 1099 (C.E. 1042) was composed by Brāhmaṇa Mātrasarmā, the son of Hari (no. 62). Bhādūnd stone inscription of the time of Pūrnapāla: V.S. 1102 (C.E. 1045) is the composition of Ambāditya Vyāsa, the son of Upādhyāya Mādhava of the Kāúyapa *gotra*, who composed it through the grace of Sarasvatī (no. 63). The revered and the illustrious, Tilakaprabhasūri was the poet of Jhālodī stone inscription of the time of Dhārāvarka: V.S. 1255 (C.E. 1198) (no. 73). Vaijāditya composed the Giravad stone inscription of the time of Pratāpasimha: V.S. 1344 (C.E. 1288). His parents were Pandita Dharanīdhara and Cāmpala (no. 82). Arthūnā Stone Inscription of Cāmundarāja: V.S. 1136 (C.E. 1080) told that in the Sādhāra family was born one Sumati, an earring of the goddess Bhāratī (Sarasvatī), and his son was Vijaya, whose younger brother CaAdra composed the *praceasti* (no. 84). Arthūnā image inscription of the time of Vijayarāja: V.S. 1165 (C.E. 1107) was composed by Nārāyana (no. 89) while another Arthūnā stone inscription of the same ruler: V.S. 1166 (C.E. 1109) informs us that the sixteen stanzas beginning from the fourth, along with the first were composed by the learned Kamuka while the rest (stanzas 2-3) was the work of Bhāmuka, son of the Brāhmaṇa Sāvada and grandson of Bhāilla of the Valla family (no. 90). Kirādū stone inscription of Somesvara: V.S. 1218 (C.E. 1161) states that the eulogy was composed, with the order of king, by Narasimha (no. 94).

The author of the records many times wrote it in the sense that they gave the final draft of the record to the scribe who was proficient for writing

or copying it on stone, metal and other similar objects with a skilful hand⁶. For clear and beautiful writing of the royal inscription, in general, skilled scribes were employed⁷. Of the scribes of the Paramâra inscriptions, Gunadhara was the Kâyastha who had written the two Harsolâ copper-plate grants of Sîyaka: V.S. 1005 (C.E. 949) (no. 1-2). Chaddaka, son of Amnaka was the writer of the Modâsâ copper-plate inscription of the time of Bhojadeva: V.S. 1067 (C.E. 1011) (no. 8). The charter is neither carefully engraved nor shows the symmetry or beauty in formation. British Museum image inscription of Bhojadeva: V.S. 1091 (C.E. 1034) was written by Sivadeva (no. 14). The minister of peace and war, the illustrious Jogeœvara of the twice born race was the writer of Kâlvan copper-plate inscription of the time of Bhojadeva (no. 16). Dongaragâon stone inscription of the time of Jagaddeva: Saka Samvat 1034 (C.E. 1112) was written by Viúvsvâmin (no. 28). Pandita Râjapâla has written the Amerâ stone inscription of the time of Naravarman: V.S. 1151 (C.E. 1094) (no. 30). Arthûnâ stone inscription of Câmundarâja: V.S. 1136 (C.E. 1080) told that *prasasti* was written on stone by Âsarâja, a son of Srîdhara, a Kâyastha belonging to the Vâlabhya (hailing from Valabhi) family (no. 84). However, other Arthûnâ image inscription of V.S. 1165 (C.E. 1107) was written by Anamta (no. 89). Ropî inscription of Devarâja: V.S. 1059 (C.E. 1012) was written by Sûryaravî, a son of Nyâsa (no. 91). Kirâdû stone inscription of Somesvara: V.S. 1218 (C.E. 1161) states that the eulogy was written by Yaúodeva (no. 94). Some correction was also done after aware of the fault. For example, in line 29 of Mândhâtâ copper-plate (no. 51, plate XLIX) „*kâtyâyana gotrâya* was left that was added between the lines 28-29 in smaller shape.

Inscriptions of the Paramâras also furnish information regarding their engravers, listed here. The record of the Jhâlrapâman stone inscription of the time of Udayâditya: V.S. 1143 (C.E. 1087)

is stated to have been engraved by Pandita Harcuka (no. 22). Amerâ stone inscription of the time of Naravarman: V.S. 1151 (C.E. 1094) was inscribed by Saumatika (no. 30). Vidishâ stone inscription of Trailokyavarman: V.S. 1216 (C.E. 1158) was engraved by Vâsudeva (no. 42). Sehore copper-plate inscriptions of Arjunavarman were engraved by Pandita Bâpyadeva (nos. 48, 49). The artisan (*rûpakâra*) Kânhada was the engraver of two Mândhâtâ copper-plate inscriptions (nos. 57, 60). Dhâmna, son of *sûtradhâra* Sarûka was the engraver of the Varmân stone inscription of the time of Pûrnâpâla: V.S. 1099 (C.E. 1043) (no. 61), while Vasantagadha stone inscription of the time of same ruler was engraved by Úivapâla, who was the son of the *sûtradhâra* Deuka, the grandson of Durga and the great-grandson of the *sthapati* (architect) Nâga (no. 62). Dhâreúvara, Deua, Devau and Lahampa were the engravers of Pûrnâpâla s Bhâdund stone inscription of V.S. 1102 (C.E. 1045) and possibly also the excavators of the well (no. 63). Ajhârî stone inscription of the time of Yasodhava: V.S. 1202 (C.E. 1146) was engraved by *sûtradhâra* Câdadeva (no. 64). In the end of the Kâmtal stone inscription of the time of Dhârâvarca: V.S. 1274 (C.E. 1216) the name of Mahidhara appears who might be the engraver of the inscription (no. 75). Girvad stone inscription of the time of Pratâpasimha: V.S. 1344 (C.E. 1288) was engraved by Gâmgadeva, son of Sûmadeva, a resident of Rohedâ (no. 82). Pânâhedâ stone inscription of Mandalîka: V.S. 1116 (C.E. 1059) was engraved by Asarâja, a son of Srîdhara, who belonged to the Vâlabhya Kâyastha family (no. 83). Arthûnâ stone inscription of Câmundarâja: V.S. 1136 (C.E. 1080) told that the eulogy was engraved by *sûtradhâra* Gumdâka, a son of *sûtradhâra* Nannâ (no. 84). Nânâka was the engraver of the Arthûnâ image inscription of the time of Vijayarâja: V.S. 1165 (C.E. 1107), who also carved the image of Hanumâna (no. 89), while *vijñânika* Sûmâka was the engraver of another

Arhûnâ stone inscription of the time of same ruler: V.S. 1166 (C.E. 1109) (no. 90). Kirâdû stone inscription of Someúvara: V.S. 1218 (C.E. 1161) states that the eulogy was engraved by Yaúodhara (no. 94). The information about Pandita Harcuka, Pandita Râjapâla and others reveal that the profession of engraving became respectable at that time.

Nâgarî Alphabet:

Inscriptions of the Paramâras are written in Nâgarî characters. Regional cultures, personal mannerisms, efforts at speed, beautification and decoration and the writing materials and tools are some of the factors which explain the differences and characteristics of Nâgarî alphabet in the Paramâra inscriptions. As for the professionals, individual mannerism has an effect on the writing. In general, the engraver incised the letters according to the drawing of the scribe to retain the accuracy and perform his work neatly. However, due to an illiterate or unskilled engraver sometimes the form of the letter is misshapen. On the other hand, it is easier to draw wedge head-mark, thin and thick line by wedged pen while linear head-mark and uniformity in thickness may be easily drawn by stylus pen. Difference in progress of writing also might be observed in term of centre and periphery. Naturally, the skilled professionals of the court were more skilled and well aware with the latest development than those of the remote places.

Nâgarî script, also known by the name Devanâgarî, is the most popular script of India, is now used over a large part of Indian subcontinent for writing Sanskrit and some other Indian languages, though it is seldom realised by the common people that its origin lies in Brâhmî through a chain of successive evolution⁸. However, passing through its various developmental stages, some or the other part of every letter of the Mauryan Brâhmî is still retained

in the Nâgarî forms, with only some ornamental or simplified additions and modifications. From Mauryan to mid of the sixth century C.E. only a few letters resembled counterparts in Nâgarî. Most of the letters from the seventh century onwards underwent the process of development in their formation which mislead some scholars to consider that Nâgarî begin in the eighth-ninth centuries or even more earlier⁹. Moreover, passing through its developmental stages in north India Brâhmî grew into a script called by the palaeographers as Siddhamâtrka, Kumila, acute-angled, etc¹⁰. The new innovation, by which it differs from Brâhmî, is the inward bending in the vertical limbs of the letter resulting in the formation of an acute-angle with the base line on the right end of some letters. In addition, the top of the letters grow into a triangular shape and the medial signs prolong with twists and bends. These features are developed mainly due to the pen technique which can be seen in the forms of the letters that become more decorative in the medial signs¹¹. The main features of the Kumila script remained almost the same excepting for ornamentation. The ornamentation and the shape of letters differ in different regions due to the writing materials, regional traits, as well as personal habits and mannerisms of the scribes¹². In the last phase of seventh century more advanced letter forms developed, which paved the way for Nâgarî and is now called by the name proto-Nâgarî. In proto-Nâgarî, the triangular head-mark become broader, or is replaced by a small stroke, and tail or footmark is developed at the bottom of the letters. Most of the earliest proto-Nâgarî specimens reveal the mixture of triangular and linear type of head-mark. The writing material and writing technique played an important role in the emergence of the simple forms of the writing and Nâgarî alphabet. The main characteristics of Nâgarî, i.e. full covering head-line, straight vertical, uniform medial signs, mutilated consonant in ligature and *halanta* sign,

is exhibited in Bhârat Kalâ Bhavan copper-plate inscription of Pratihâra Harirâja (C.E. 983)¹³ and Kauthom plates of Caulukya Vikramâditya V (C.E. 1008)¹⁴. The script of these epigraphs approaches the mature Nâgarî form which is fully developed by the 13th century C.E. But it does not mean that the Nâgarî of the 13th century is same as of the 21st century¹⁵ and since no development took place in the form of the letters.

To discuss the Nâgarî alphabet and numerals signs, I have selected seventeen inscriptions of the Paramâras of different branches that are represented in sixteen columns, of which signs of two inscriptions are in column ten and of one in each column. Of them, ten inscriptions, represented in nine columns (1, 2, 4, 6, 10, 11, 13, 14, 15) belongs to the Paramâras of Mâlava, three (columns 3, 9, 16) to the Paramâras of Mount Âbû or Candrâvatî, one (column 12) to the Paramâras of Bhinmâl, one (column 8) to the Paramâras of Jâlôr and two (columns 5, 7) to the Paramâras of Vâgada. Here, I indicate only some unusual features and need not go into the details of the formation of the individual letters in different periods and localities as the tables (I-III) are self-explanatory. Among noticeable features, Harsolâ inscriptions of Siyaka (column 1) display an interesting feature about the head-strokes of the letters. Most of them show curvatures of zigzags in the middle and a few looks like a small crescent. The left limb of the initial *a* curve with a slanting stroke below and sporadically it also represents a form in which the curve is surmounted by a small vertical stroke and looks like counterpart in Nâgarî. Initial *i* is shown by two loops placed horizontally and subscribed by the sign for medial *u* ending in a sharp curve below. Of the consonants, *kha* is represented by two triangle joined by a horizontal line above. The forelimb of *ga* is also formed as a triangle with its apex above. The letter *Ga* looks like the modern *la*. The letters *gha*, *ca*, *ja*, *ta*, *na*, *bha* and *œa* continued their traditional shape. Of

the two forms of *dha*, in one the left limb of the letter is endowed with a horn above, but generally this letter is without the horn. The peculiar form of *pha* in *phalam* line²⁴, differs entirely from other form of the record. There are variations in the representation of letter *ra*, one formed by a vertical stroke with a horizontal bar attached to its middle on the left, another with the bar originated from the top stroke itself and the third with the horizontal stroke has a wedged attached to it in the middle. As for the medial signs, *a* sometimes replaced by a crescent attached to the right extremity of the top stroke of a letter. The vertical of the medial short *i* is often slightly bent to the right at the bottom. Medial *e* is also in crescent or twisted top stroke form. Above all, the characters show a transitional stage. The letters and medial signs of the Ganorî copper-plate inscription of Vâkpatirâja (column 2) are more cursive. Initial *a* is formed by the sign of the initial *u* joined to a vertical stroke with a horizontal and a footmark below. Initial *i* is represented by two circles subscribed by the medial sign *u*. Of the consonants, *Ea* has not developed a dot, and *ca*, *dha*, *va* are almost alike in form; *kha*, *cha*, *ja*, *na*, *bha* and *œa* continued their old forms. The letter *ña* is similar to *Ga*. As for medial signs, ornamentation might be observed in the formation of *e*. Further, in the Vasantagadh inscription (column 3) initial *i* is denoted by two dots, subscribed by medial *u* like symbol the tail of which is extended in hook form on the top of the dots; *Ea* is without dot and there is no apparent difference in the forms of *ca*, *dha* and *va*, but *ba* has a separate sign of its own. The letters *kha*, *ta*, *la* and *sa* have generally not developed the tail of the left limb. The difference between the forms of the palatal and dental sibilant is often marked in that the form of these is engraved with a tail of the left which is missing in the latter. The letters are not deeply engraved so that occasionally the impression shows only dots of the loops of letters *na* and *ma*, with the strokes overall missing. The

medial *a* is often denoted by a stroke above the top of a letter, and occasionally the form of short and long medial *i* is only a curve above the top and not taken below. Sometimes, the strokes of the medial signs have been ornamentally treated (table III, column 3) and there are some decorative designs in lines 21-22 and at the end of the inscription.

The engraver of the Tilakwādā inscription (column 4) has fared very slovenly in his task and the expected shape of the letters are often transformed, a number of them also received the arbitrary touch of the chisel. It is also of noteworthy that the writing is sparser on the last two sides in comparison with the first. As far the forms of the letters, in archaic form initial *i* is shown by three dots, two above and one below, initial long *ū* is presented by adding a curved stroke in the middle of the short *u*, initial *e* is almost a triangle with the vertical point below while *ai* is denoted by adding medial sign *e* in its form, *dha* and *va* are more or less similar in form, *œa* is sometimes devoid of the slanting stroke below and head-mark. Likewise, the Pânâhedâ inscription (column 5) display initial *i* represented by two hollow circles subscribed by the sign for the medial short *u* and the same vowel in its long form is distinguished by a horizontal stroke above. The letter *Ea* is still without dot and the letters *ca*, *dha* and *va* are looks like similar in form. The rare *jhā* is shown which is similar in formation to the modern *kra*. The form of the letters *ta*, *na*, *va* and *la* are occasionally confused with each other, which might be due to an error on the part of the scribe or the engraver. Furthermore, *pa* has similar form as *ya*, and *bha* is often baffled with *ha*. Distinction between the formation of palatal *sa* and dental *sa* is that the loop which begins the first of these letters assumes the form of a stroke curved above whereas that of the second is curved downwards. Both these letters are in a transitional state, rarely assuming the modern forms.

The general peculiarity of the Jhâlrâpâman inscription (column 6) is that the vertical of letters and the *prcmhamâtrâ* shows a sudden bend to the right at their lower extremity. The initial *i* is formed of two circles placed side by side with hooks in the opposite directions with some ornamentation below, triangular form of initial *e* is yet to develop its tail, *kha* is formed of two loops suspended by vertical strokes, the top of which are joined by a horizontal line and left limb is without tail, the right portion of *gha* is still to move below to develop modern form, *dha* has not developed a horn on the top of its left limb, the loops of *na* and *ma* are often below, and the fore limbs of *ha* and *ta* ends in sharp tail, *tha* is formed of two hollows placed vertically before a horizontal stroke, *ra* is generally wedged while *bha* is rather peculiarly formed. Letters *ca*, *cha*, *ja*, *œa* and *sa* are yet to develop modern form. Some ornamentation is noticed in the formation of medial sign *e*. Further, Arthûnâ inscription (column 7) shows the form of initial *a* which has begun assuming its modern shape, and the initial short *i* is represented by two dots followed by a sign like medial *u* while long *i* is denoted by three dots and a rightward hook in lower left, *ca* is distinguished from *va* in showing its loop angular, The letters *kha*, *gha*, *ja*, *bha* and *sa* are in developed or developing forms while without horn *dha* still continues to resemble *va*. Jâlor inscription (column 8) display initial *a* begin with a dome-shaped curve and *i* is in older form, letter *pa* and *ya* have often the matching form, *dha* continues its antique form without horn, *ra* is in transitional stage, and other letters are almost in developed Nâgarî form.

Giravad stone inscription (column 9) represent antique form of initial *i* and *cha*, *bha* is in transitional form, while other letters shows developed counterparts in modern Nâgarî, whereas there is some ornamentation in the formation of medial *e*. As far the forms of letters of Ujjain inscriptions (column 10) initial *i* is formed

by a horizontal stroke, with ends slightly curved below, in level with the top strokes, and subscribed by a sign resembling the medial *u*, initial *ai* is represented by adding a sign of medial *e* in the form of initial *e*, *ca* is occasionally distinguished by a triangular loop from *va*, but *bha* and *ha* are sometimes written alike in which the slanting stroke of the second of these letters is missing; the right limb of *ja* is yet to develop vertical form.

Sarpa-bandha inscriptions from Ujjain, Dhâr and Ûn are of educational significance, also showing the high interest of the public in teaching and learning grammar. Of them, I have selected the Ujjain Mahâkâla temple inscription (column 11) which dedicates the *varna-nâgakrpânikâ* to Udayâditya. This serpentine sword of king Udayâditya, intended to for the protection of letters or learning and social classes has been set up as a badge for the poets and kings. The inscription mentions that the string of poetic gems was composed by *vandhu* of the talented poets "*sukavivandhuna*", presumably refers to king Naravarman himself, who appears to have composed the *prâçastî*¹⁶. Lines 18-19 comprise the letters of Nâgarî alphabet, class-wise, each group being followed by a numerical indication showing the number of letters in it. Thus the number 14 in line 18 indicates the vowels from *a* to *au*, then the number 2 the *anusvâra* and *visarga*, and following it, again the number 2 is engraved at the end of the sign of *jihvâmuliya* and *upadhamânîya*. Line 19 consist the consonants from *ka* to *ha*, signifying their total number 51 at the end. The subtotal is also pointed out just after each of the groups. Line 20 of the inscription offers the long vowels *â, î, û,]*, and *l]* and following these, in lines 20-22 the well known *Mâheûvara-sûtras*. At the end of *Mâheûvara-sûtra* begins the *bandha*, was known as *vamanâga-krpânikâ*, which is, as expression indicates, a scimitar or a dagger formed by the combination of the letters and a snake (no. 25). The characters of the Mahâkâla

inscription (column 11) are beautifully written and deeply engraved. As far the individual letters is concerned, *Ea* is devoid of dot, dental *dha* has begun to developing a horn, *da* is formed so as to resemble *ra*, *ba* has a separate sign of its own that resembling a parallelogram. It is of noteworthy that in the alphabetical list letters *pha* and *bha* are in archaic forms while in lines 3 and 15 respectively their modern and developing Nâgarî form is engraved.

Kirâdû inscription (column 12) displays the developed form of most of the letters, except the letters *ja* and *bha* which continue their old forms. Examples of wrong stroke of the chisel are occasionally to be noticed in the formation of *ma*, *da*, and *va*. Bhopâl inscription (column 13) display initial *a* begins with a semi-circular form, first curved above and then bent below, *i* is in archaic circles and hook form, medial *e* of initial *ai* shows ornamental features, left limb of *ca* is triangular but yet to develop upper leftward extension, dental *dha* has developed a horn on its left limb which is in stroke or more developed curved form. There are some confusion in the forms between *pa* and *ya*, again in *ra* and *ca*. Letters *ja* and *bha* are in the process of development. Further development could be seen in the Mândhâtâ inscription (column 14) where *a* is formed by placing a curve below another and superimposed by a vertical stroke, *i* is formed of two loops placed side by side with a fine bend below and thus being almost as a precursor of the modern letter, *e* is formed by two curved horizontal lines with their ends joined and the initial *au* by joining the upper loop of *a* with the vertical by a bar, loop of *ca* is developing left stroke as in modern Nâgarî, and the initial top-stroke of *dha* shows a beautiful bend, represents developed stage, but *tha* is engraved as *vva* while *ja* and *bha* are in transitional form. Medial *e* is in both, top-stroke as well in *prcmhamâtrâ* form. Another Mândhâtâ inscription (column 15) displays the letters in developed forms. Initial *i* show a form

which is precursor of the Nāgarī counterpart, initial *e* with its vertical not fully developed occasionally resembles the letter *pa*, and the initial *o* almost resembles the same symbol of inscription at the beginning. The initial *l* is in modern shape. The letters *cha*, *ja* and *bha* have almost begun to

assume its modern form while others shown developed shape. Giravad inscription (column 16) exhibit developed form of the signs of vowels and consonants, though the persistence of ornamental feature in the medial sign *e* is of noteworthy.

Vowels Signs

Table-I

Key	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
A	अ	अ	अ	अ	अ	अ	अ		अ	अ	अ	अ	अ	अ	अ	अ
Ā		आ	आ	आ	आ		आ	आ		आ	आ		आ	आ	आ	आ
I	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ	इ		इ	इ	इ	इ
Ī					इ		इ				इ			इ		
U	उ	उ		उ	उ	उ	उ		उ	उ	उ	उ	उ	उ	उ	उ
Ū				उ							उ			उ	उ	
R											र				र	
E		ए	ए	ए	ए	ए			ए		ए			ए	ए	ए
Ai				ऐ						ऐ	ऐ		ऐ			
O											उ				उ	
Au											अ			अ		

Consonants Signs

Table-II A

Key	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Ka	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क	क
Kha	ख	ख	ख	ख	ख	ख	ख		ख	ख	ख	ख	ख	ख	ख	ख
Ga	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग	ग
Gha	घ	घ		घ	घ	घ	घ		घ	घ	घ		घ		घ	
Na		ङ	ङ		ङ		ङ				ङ	ङ				
Ca	च	च		च	च	च	च	च	च	च	च	च	च	च	च	च
Cha		छ		छ	छ	छ	छ		छ		छ	छ	छ	छ	छ	
Ja	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज	ज
Jha				झ							झ					
Na		ण									ण				ण	
Ta	ट	ट		ट	ट		ट		ट	ट	ट	ट	ट	ट	ट	ट
Tha		ठ	ठ	ठ	ठ				ठ	ठ	ठ	ठ		ठ	ठ	ठ
Da	ड	ड		ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड	ड
Dha		ढ		ढ			ढ			ढ	ढ			ढ	ढ	
Na	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न
Ta	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त	त

Consonants Signs

Table-II B

Tha	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ	थ
Da	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द	द
Dha	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध	ध
Na	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न	न
Pa	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प	प
Pha	फ	फ		फ	फ			फ	फ	फ		फ	फ	फ	
Ba			ब							ब					
Bha	भ	भ		भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ	भ
Ma	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म	म
Ya	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य	य
Ra	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र	र
La	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल	ल
Va	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व	व
Ṣa	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष	ष
Ṣa	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श	श
Sa	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स	स
Ha	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह	ह

Numeral Signs:

Like alphabets, the Indian numeral also reveals a history of gradual evolution. Before the tenth century C.E. numeral notations were denoted in two ways—letter numerals and numeral figures of the decimal system. In letter numerals separate signs are used for the units, tens, hundreds and thousands. Other composite numbers are represented by the combination of units with tens, hundreds and thousands. This type of notation was employed exclusively up to the later part of the 6th century C.E. and thereafter sporadically survived alongside the decimal system till the 10th century C.E. Very useful researches on the letter-numerals have been done by E. Thomas¹⁷, E. Clive Bayley¹⁸, Bhau Daji¹⁹, H. R. Kapadia²⁰, Bhagawanlal Indrajit²¹, G. Buhler²², G. S. Ojha²³, Awdhesh Narain Singh²⁴, Sobhana Laxaman Gokhale²⁵ and Om Prakash Lal Srivastava²⁶.

The modern system of using nine unit figures and zero for all purposes of notation and calculation, arranged in decimal order seems to be of a later period. To the best of our knowledge, the earliest epigraphic instance of the use of the decimal notation is the Gurjjara inscriptions from Sankhedâ of Cedi year 346 (C.E. 14 595). Here, neither I am going to deal with the typology, old and new of the numerals nor wish to enter into the controversy of numerals being evolved with the letter forms or independent symbols but have taken the general resemblance of the numeral signs with the letters of the period and trace the history of evolution of Nâgarî Numerals of Paramâra inscriptions (table IV).

The sign of zero is circular in shape as in modern times. Sometimes it is oval. The earlier numeral 1 is denoted by a vertically placed stroke. In further developmental stage a hook, a knob or a small circle is added to the top of it. Out of them, small circular variety is accepted in modern Nâgarî. Sign for 2 is two parallel horizontal strokes joined by a third cursive stroke and added with a slanting stroke. Old form of the numeral notation

3 is formed with three parallel horizontal lines. In the first developmental stage right tip of the upper two bars slant to meet with the lower bar, which is extended to the right. The further developmental stage shows a form in which the right tip of both upper bars became cursive by which three limbs joined with each other. Finally, from the 9th century, upper two lines are shortened and form almost a double curved shape and a slanted tail is attached at the lower extremity. This form is retained in Nâgarî. The modern form of the sign for 4 occurs in 9th century, before that it was represented by a sign like letter *ka* or ligature *pka*. The numeral 5 is represented by a sign of letter *ja* or an upward curve with notched left limb. The next developmental stage shows a straight line at the right but left limb still is notched. Finally the right limb became straight and the left one cursive. From this form modern Nâgarî shape evolved in due course of time. The earlier specimens frequently show the letter form of *ja* for the numeral notation 6. In the further developmental stage, upper curve is turned to right and lower slanted stroke develops into a hook shape and finally both limbs of the vertical become cursive with a vertical tail. In tracing the development of Nâgarî numeral 7 it is observed that it was shown by a downward curve in the earlier period. In developing stages, the right limb of the curve extends downward, progressively turned to left in various degrees and finally prolongs upwards. To trace the developmental stages of Nâgarî form of numeral 8, earlier it is represented as a rightward curve, gradually upper portion become flattened with a downward slanted stroke, lower slant transforms into a rightward curve and finally upper flat line produces to the left. This shape is still employed in Nâgarî. Generally two signs are employed for numeral 9 in later period. Of these, first is leftward hooked shape with a circle at the upper end and second is double curved shape. Second shape furnished numerous sub-varieties which could be understood by the illustrations (table IV).

Numerals Signs

Table-IV

Key	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
0	०	०			०	०	०		०		०	०		०	०	०
1		१			१	१	१	१	१	१	१	१	१	१	१	१
2		२			२		२		२	२	२	२	२	२	२	२
3	३	३			३	३	३		३	३	३	३		३	३	३
4		४			४	४	४	४	४		४	४		४	४	४
5	५	५			५		५	५	५		५	५	५	५	५	५
6					६		६		६		६	६	६	६	६	६
7					७		७	७	७		७	७		७	७	७
8		८			८		८		८		८	८		८	८	८
9					९		९		९	९	९			९	९	९

Other Signs:

In the Paramâras inscriptions several signs and symbols are to be found and very often we are not sure about the phonetic or symbolic value of these signs. Some scholars read the signs found in the beginning of the inscriptions as *siddham* and other prefers to read them as sign for *om*. There are also signs for *Jihvâmûliya* and *Upadhamâniya*. As for the punctuation marks, it is generally averred that the various modern signs of punctuation were not employed in the inscriptions, true to some extent. A *danda* or stroke is drawn to mark the completion of a sentence or a hemistich of a verse and two *dandas* or strokes

to indicate the completion of a verse. Some *mangalas* and ornamental signs are also drawn in the later portion; or at the end of the inscriptions. A very common sign of this description is a large circle with a smaller one in side.

Depiction of Garud a and Siva:

As for the religious and moral sphere, the Paramâras personified the best in their dominions that left behind a great tradition of religious tolerance. Hinduism and Jainism thrived side by side in peace and harmony and Jaina scholars also received as much recognition at the courts as Brâhmanas. The Brahmanical Hinduism was

flourishing and popularizing with the help of the Paramâra rulers who constructed temples dedicated to the Hindu deities in their sovereignty and donated land-grants to the Brâhmanas. Visnu was the ideal god and Bhoja was Tribhuvana-nârâyana while Naravarman called himself Nirvâna-nârâyana or Nirbhaya-nârâyana. Siyaka was a devotee of Visnu, invokes the blessings of Visnu in Narasingha incarnation. His son and successor Vâkpati makes obeisance to Murâri, i.e. Krsna. King Naravarman took pride in adopting the title Nirvâna-nârâyana. The Nâgapur inscription of the time of Naravarman pays reverence to the different incarnation of Visnu. King Arjunavarman is said to have worshiped Visnu, the husband of Laksmî. A fragmentary inscription from Mândû records highly poetical description of god Visnu in his different incarnation. King Jaitugi is called a young Nârâyana, and king Jayavarman makes obeisance to Parasurâma, Râma and Kaitabhajit. Besides, Paramâra rulers had Visnu vehicle Garuda on their seal²⁷. But the worship of Siva and Sakti was more influential. Bhoja is described as a zealous Saiva, and was the composer of a work entitled *Tatvaprakâûa*, expounding the principles of Saivism. It appears that due to the royal patronage this sect of Hinduism was spread far and wide in the whole region. Udaipur *prasasti* stating that Bhojadeva made the world worthy of its name by covering it all round with temples dedicated to Siva in the names of Kedâra, Râmesvara, Somanâtha, Sundira, Kâla, Anala and Rudra. The activity of building temples in honor of Siva and the other deities is renowned to persist throughout the widespread dominions of the Paramâras and their feudatories. The temple building activity which was prevalent during the period throughout the entire region and the fabulous elegance revealed in sculptures profusely to be found in the whole region, furnish evidence of the superb stone art and architecture. Apart from the stone art, the

copper-plate inscriptions reveal an artistic representation of Garuda.

Most of the copper-plates of the Paramâras of Mâlava bear the representation of Garuda, which seems to be their royal emblem. Mostly, Garuda is shown at the end of the inscription, but in a few cases represented in the centre of the plate. Some variations are also of noteworthy in the forms of Garuda. A figure of flying Garuda holding a snake in his left arm and with right hand raised above is shown in the second Harsolâ plate (Photo 1). There is a flying Garuda facing right and depicted as a human being, except for the wings attached to his shoulders, holding a hooded snake in his left hand and right hand is raised displayed in the lower portion of the second plate of Ahmedâbâd grant. The figure measures about 5 cm. in height and 4 cm. in breadth. The lower left corner of the second plate of Dharampurî grant (Photo 2), in a rectangular space of about 9 cm. high by 8 cm. broad, shows the figure of a flying Garuda, in human form and facing left, holding snake in the left hand. The figure is well executed, wearing an ornamented crown and other ornaments such as anklets, armlets, and necklace. Almost in the identical form flying Garuda (8x11 cm.) is incised on the bottom of the third Ganorî copper-plate, wearing an ornamented crown, other ornaments and a long garland, holding a snake in the left hand, with the right one raised up. Here, the snake is shown in coiled form. The technical execution is neat and clean, as comprehensible from the photograph (Photo 3). The figure of the flying Garuda on Mahaudî copper-plate is not obvious but appears with a circular object held up in the left hand. In the lower left part of the second plate of Bemmâ (Photo 4) a rectangle (5.5x7.3 cm.) is formed by double lines interspaced by oblique strokes ending in acute angles, and there is a representation of Garuda in kneeling position, facing left wearing a turban like head-dress and holding a snake in the left hand. Bânsiwâdâ copper-

plate also shows a rectangular form with the representation of a flying Garuda (8x6 cm.), and a snake in the left hand and the right being raised above. There is representation of a flying Garuda with head-dress, a snake in the left hand and the raised right hand in the Ujjain copper-plate. The design is enclosed in a rectangle of double lines inter-spaced with oblique strokes. An area of 10.5 cm. square in the left lower corner of the second Depâlpur plate is occupied by a rectangle containing the figure of a flying and left facing Garuda that is not much clear. The lower portion of the second Mândhâtâ plate (Photo 5) shows a representation of a flying Garuda (6.35x7 cm.) with the body of a man and an oblique nose, facing left and looking at a serpent held in his left hand. On the lower side of the second Kadambapadraka plate (Photo 6) is engraved the figure of Garuda (7x9 cm.) facing left and kneeling, with wings spread and holding a hooded snake in left hand two snakes in right hand and one snake is shown in the neck. The figure of Garuda is adorned with head-dress, ear-rings and long garland. The Ujjain plate (Photo 7) display in the lower left portion a rectangle formed of double lines (10.5x9.5 cm.), contains a depiction of Garuda in human form and with a pointed nose, kneeling facing front but head turned to left. The image holds three snakes in the left hand and the right hand rose up. Furthermore, in the centre of the second Bhopâl plate (Photo 8), in a square of 6 cm is engraved the figure of a Garuda in human form kneeling and facing proper left, wearing crown. The figure is represented between pillars on left and right side. The second Bhopâl plate (Photo 9) formed double plain border in the lower middle of lines 34 to 41, with the figure of Garuda in human form but with the nose of a bird, facing front, wear long garland and unique head-dress. The head of the figure is turned to right and the hand joined near the chest, as in devotion. The Mândhâtâ plate (Photo 10) shows a representation of Garuda with folded

hands and facing left, carved between two snakes, in a double bordered rectangular space of 5.2x7 cm. On the reverse of the second Mândhâtâ plate (Photo 11), between lines 42 and 50, a vertical line marks of 10.2x8 cm., contains an engraving of Garuda, is represented in human form with four hands, the upper two hands are folded over the chest, the lower right lifted up with fingers raised and the lower left raised with holding a snake, kneeling towards the left but with the head turned towards right. The figure has a bird's beak nose, rose up hair, bearded face, and adorned with necklace, armlets and anklets. It also wears a scarf in the neck and an upper garment with flaring ends. In a square measuring 19 cm. of the reverse of the fourth Mândhâtâ plate is a depiction of Garuda. The space covered by figure is 13x11 cm. and in technical execution it resembles the one engraved on the inscription of the same king from the same place (no. 57). The image is enshrined in a structure with a plain rectangular pillar divided into three parts, on either side, and supporting the roof which consists of three superimposed slabs, which, in their turn, support the spire, like a miniature shrine as was in vogue in Mâlava during that time. The exact shape of it may be seen from the photograph (Photo 12). The Râjpur plate exhibit a roughly engraved figure of Garuda in human form (5x4 cm.), kneeling and facing left, with folded hands. Here, the conspicuous aspect is that the letters Garuda is engraved near its face in Nâgarî characters. On the whole, the entire representation of the Garuda in copper-plates inscriptions of the Paramâras of Mâlava, developed a style of its own, similarity might be observed with *ApabhraAsa* style of paintings.

Apart from the figure of Garuda, representation of Úiva is also noticed. The lower part of the Harsaudâ stone (Photo 13) bears a crude depiction of Úiva, in a double lined rectangle with beaded sides, 6.5 cm. broad and 4.5 cm. high. On its right side there are three and on left side

Medial Signs

Table-III

Key	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
Ā	पा	वा	र्क	दा	रा	डा	णा	मा	ला	दा	वा	पा	का	दा	वा	मा
I	रि	ए	कि	ति	वि	दि	नि	वि	शि	मि	ति	नि	धि	नि	लि	रि
ī	मी	शी	ली	शी	पी	पी	शी	यी	वी	शी	णी	नी	दी	री	णी	शी
U	गु	खु	सु	न	मु	दु	नु	तु	रु	वु	पु	दु	गु	रु	कु	उ
ū	रू	सू	प्रू	रू	वू	भू	रू	रू	प्रू	प्रू	रू	रू	सू	यू	प्रू	सू
R	ए	रु	शु	कृ	शु		रु	रु	शु	रु	रु	रु	कृ	शु	रु	रु
E	के	रे	रे	से	ले	ने	ते	मे	ते	दे	ले	वे	ते	वे	ते	रे
Ai	के	वे	के	सै	रे	ते	के	ने	ते	जे	वे	वे	के	ते	ते	वे
O	भा	मे	मे	को	ल	दा	मी	को	ली	ला	ला	रो	शी	मी	सो	यो
Au	यो	लो	के	दो	को		ते	मी	दी			गे	दो	लो	पो	को

four figures of males and females of about the same height, who are paying devotion to Siva. It is plausible that they might be the members of a family of the person who built the temple referred to in record as construction of a temple of Sambhu by one Kesava.

Index of the palaeographical tables (I-IV)

These tables contain sixteen columns, properly numbered. Each column bears vowel signs, consonant signs, medial signs and numeral signs of a class of inscriptions which are given below:

1. Harasolâ Copper-plate Grant of Siyaka (Vikrama) year 1005 (C.E.949), Harihar Vitthal Trivedi, 1978 *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum (CII): Inscriptions of the Paramâras*, Vol. VII-Part 2, New Delhi, no. 1, plate I.
2. Ganorî Copper-plate Inscription of Vâkpatirâjâdeva: year 1038 (C.E. 981), *CII*, VII, no. 6, plates V-VI.
3. Vasantagadh Stone Inscription of the time of PûrGapâla: year 1099 (C.E. 1042), *CII*, VII, no. 62, plate LXV.
4. Tilakwâdâ Copper-plate Inscription of the time of Bhojadeva: year 1103 (C.E. 1046), *CII*, VII, no. 15, plates XVI B-XVII.
5. Pânâhedâ Stone Inscription of Mandalîka: year 1116 (C.E. 1059), *CII*, VII, no. 83, plate LXXXIII.
6. Jhâlrâpâman Stone Inscription of the time of Udayâditya: year 1143 (C.E. 1086), *CII*, VII, no. 22, plate XXIII.
7. Arthûnâ Stone Inscription of the time of Vijayarâja: year 1166 (C.E. 1109), *CII*, VII, no. 90, plate LXXXIX.
8. Jâlor Stone Inscription of the time of Visala: year 1174 (C.E. 1118), *CII*, VII, no. 96, plate

XCII.

9. Giravad Stone Inscription of the time of PratâpasiAha: year 1181 (CE 1124), *CII*, VII, Part 3, no. 187, plate XCIII.
10. Ujjain Copper-plate Inscription of Yacœvarman: year 1192 (C.E. 1135), *CII*, VII, no. 38, plate XL A; Ujjain Copper-plate Inscription of Jayavarman, *CII*, VII, no. 39, plate XL B
11. Ujjain Mahâkâlêûvara Temple Sarpabandha Inscription, *CII*, VII, no. 25, plate XXVII.
12. Kirâdû Stone Inscription of Someœvara: year 1218 (C.E. 1161), *CII*, VII, no. 94, plate XC.
13. Bhopâl Copper-plate Inscription of Mahâkumâra Udayavarman: year 1256 (C.E. 1200), *CII*, VII, no. 46, plates XLVI-XLVII.
14. Mândhâtâ Copper-plate Inscription of Devapâla: year 1282 (C.E. 1225), *CII*, VII, no. 51, plates XLIX-L.
15. Mândhâtâ Copper-plate Inscription of Jayavarman: year 1331 (C.E. 1274), *CII*, VII, no. 60, plates LX-LXIII.
16. Giravad Stone Inscription of the time of PratâpsiAha: year 1344 (C.E. 1287), *CII*, VII, no. 82, plate LXXXII.

Notes and References:

1. On the basis of the verse 24 of the Sanjan copper-plates inscription of Amoghavarsha dated 871 C.E. (*Epigraphia Indica*, XVIII, pp. 235-57), it has been concluded by Harihar Vitthal Trivedi, (1991 *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum*, VII-1, p.2) that Govind III entrusted the charge of the administration of Malava to one of his vassals, who admittedly taken to have been

Upendra, the founder of the Paramara dynasty.

2. *Indian Antiquary*, VIII, p. 11.
3. Number within brackets indicates inscription numbers in Harihar Vitthal Trivedi, 1978 *Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum: Inscriptions of the Paramaras*, VII-2, ASI, New Delhi, 1978.
4. *Epigraphia Indica*, I, p. 297.
5. It is believed that man to become a poet must equip himself with *vidya* (learning) and *upvidya* (auxiliaries). Rajasekhara mentions in the *Kavyamimamsa* (Gaekwad Oriental Series, p. 49) that grammar, lexicography, metrics and rhetoric constitute essentially 'vidya' or more precisely, 'kavyavidya', i.e. requisite learning for making poetry and the sixty four fine arts, for instance, painting, music, sculpture and so on, or „*upvidyā* or accessories: '*nama-dhatu-parayana abhidhana-kosah chandovicitih alamkara-tatranca kavya vidyah kalastu catuhsasthir upavidyah*'.
 7. Very often expert craftsmen undertook the task of engraving. The lay public, though well educated, sought to avoid writing as the scribe's handwriting was distinctly superior. This is evident from the remark of Canakya that even though written with utmost care the letters of a *Srotriya* (Vedic scholar) like himself would be far from clear (*Mudrarakshasa*, Act I) and he prefers the services of a scribe; and when the final draft is brought to him he admires the letters. For detail see, C. Sivaramamurti, 1952 *Indian Epigraphy and South Indian Scripts*, Bulletin of the Madras Government Museum, III- 4, (reprint 1966), pp. 32-35.
 8. H. K. Bhattacharya (1959, *The language and scripts of ancient India*, Calcutta, pp. 113-114) has emphatically asserted that Brahmi cannot be called the mother of Nagari and that the latter has a different origin.
 9. G. Buhler (1959 *Indian Palaeography*, Calcutta, pp. 69-70) recognised the sign-manual of Gurjara princes of the 7th-8th century as first example of Nagari, while N. N. Vasu, (*Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bombay*, LXV, pp. 128-133) takes it back into 5th century C.E.
 10. David Diringer, 1948 *The Alphabet*, London,
6. In, any of the cases, the writings were done by the professional scribe of the court and the engravers incised the letters according to drawing, although sometimes the engravers themselves wrote the text on the plates or engraved the text without drawing the letters on them. The practice of writing the text of a document on the plates first in ink is clearly indicated by Kasia copper-plate inscription, which bears 13 lines of writing of which only the first line is incised while the remaining 12 lines are written in black ink. In some records, the letters of which are painted on stone, the intention of engraving them at a later date remains unmaterialized. This was meant to facilitate the work of engraving and also to ensure

p. 357; D. C. Sircar, *Epigraphia Indica*, XXXIV, p. 161; J. Princep, *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bombay*, VI, p.779; J. F. Fleet, *Epigraphia Indica*, III, p. 328; Buhler, G. 1959 *Indian Palaeography*, p. 68.

11. c.f. A. K. Singh, 1991, *Development of Nagari Script*, Delhi, fig., 4-5.

12. A. K. Singh, 2002, "Brahmi alphabet in India and abroad (6th- 8th century C.E.): Progress of modification", *Pragdhara*, no. 12, pp. 203-220.

13. D. C. Sircar, *Epigraphia Indica*, XXXI, pp. 309-313.

14. J. F. Fleet, *Indian Antiquary*, XVI, pp.15-24.

15. A. K. Singh, 1996, "Progress of modification of Nagari alphabet as revealed by inscriptions of fourteenth-nineteenth centuries", *Pragdhara*, no. 6, pp. 189-222.

16. *Epigraphia Indica*, XXXI, p. 26, n. 4.

17. "On the Dynasty of the Sah kings of Surashtra", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, XII, pp. 32-47.

18. "On the Genealogy of modern Numerals", *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, New Series, XIV, pp. 335-376 and plate.

19. "The ancient Sanskrit Numerals in the Cave Inscriptions and on the Sah coins, correctly made out; with remarks on the Era of Salivahana and Vikramaditya", *Journal of the Bombay Branch of Royal Asiatic Society*, VIII, pp. 225-233 and plate.

20. "Foliation of Jain Manuscripts and Letter Numerals", *Annals of Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute*, XVIII, pp. 171-186 and plates.

21. "On the ancient Nagari Numerals", *Indian Antiquary*, VI, pp. 42-48 and plates.

22. *Indian Palaeography*, Calcutta, 1959, pp. 96-107 and plate.

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1. Garuḍa of Harasolā Plate (A. K. Singh)

2. Garuḍa of Dharampurī Grant (A. K. Singh)

3. Garuḍa of Ganorī Plate (A. K. Singh)

4. Garuḍa of Beṭmā Plate (A. K. Singh)